

MARGINS-I

Monitoring of Antibiotic Resistance Genes in Soils

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AUTHORS

Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety (AGES):

Sonia Galazka, MSc.; Dr. Melanie Kuffner; Mag. Karin Weyermair; Elena Radu, MSc.; Dr. Georg Dersch; Valerie Vigl, BSc; Gloria Young, BSc; Linda Tomschiczek; Dr. Juliane Pichler; Prof. Dr. Franz Allerberger; Kathrin Spettel, MSc; Richard Kriz, BSc; DI.(FH) Michael Schwarz; DI. Johann Steinwider; Harald Bock; Sonja Mika; Dr. Stefanie Dobrovolny; Mag. Rupert Hochegger; Mag. Helga Reizenzein; Dr. Richard Gottsberger; Prof. Dr. Peter Strauss; Dr. Christian Baumgartner; Ronald Hillerbrand; Mag. Karoline Zsak; Mag. Dr. Markus Wögerbauer

Technical University of Vienna (TU Wien):

Irina Dielacher, MSc.; Katarzyna Slipko, MSc.; DI. Gerhard Rab; Ass. Prof. Dr. Julia Vierheilig; Ass. Prof. Dr. Norbert Kreuzinger

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Dr. Irina Korschineck

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MARGINS-I: Monitoring of Antibiotic Resistance Genes in Soils. Identifizierung und Quantifizierung der Antibiotikaresistenzgen-Hintergrundbelastung von Böden in Österreich

Summary

Antimicrobial resistance is not only a threat for individual but also for Public Health. Many resistance genes, which are of concern in the treatment of infectious diseases, originate from environmental sources such as water and soil or from the food and feed chain. The bacterial microflora of soils is naturally abundant in antibiotic resistance genes (ARGs). Agricultural practices such as manure fertilization can introduce additional ARGs into the soil. Agroecosystems therefore play a role in the spread - but also in the containment - of resistance. Since until recently no systematically collected, quantitative data on background ARG contamination of Austrian soils were available, the **MARGINS-I** project sought to fill this data gap. In addition, the effect of manure fertilization on ARG concentrations in agricultural soils was investigated.

In a one-year longitudinal study, concentrations of **antibiotic resistance genes** were investigated in agricultural soils of an Austrian open-air experimental site (HOAL; Petzenkirchen, Lower Austria). **Four HOAL fields** were analyzed: Field F04 was not fertilized with manure during the observation period or in previous years. Fields F31 and F39 were freshly fertilized with pig manure during the study period and had also been fertilized with pig manure in previous years. Field F32 was not fertilized with manure during the observation period but had been fertilized with swine manure in previous years. Fields F04, F31 and F39 had corn grown conventionally during the observation period, and field F32 had winter wheat grown. In addition, **fresh pig faeces, pig manure, compost, drainage and stream water** were analyzed in the HOAL.

In addition, a wide range of **comparator soils** at non-agricultural sites with varying degrees of anthropogenic influence were investigated in order to place the results of the HOAL agricultural soils in this context. The comparative soils included one deciduous forest and one coniferous forest in the HOAL area, 5 coniferous forest sites in the Vienna Basin, three altitudinal levels on the Ötscher, 10 sites in the Donau-Auen National Park, and 2 deciduous forest sites and four grasslands in Vienna.

HOAL fields, HOAL drainage and stream water, and HOAL forests were sampled at 7 to 10 different time points over the duration of a vegetation period (fall 2019 to fall 2020). The comparator soil sites in Vienna and the Donau-Auen National Park were sampled in summer and winter, respectively. The sites in the Vienna Basin and at the Ötscher were analyzed only once. A total of 110 samples were analyzed, i.e. 85 soil samples, 20 water samples, 3 pig manure samples and one sample each of pig faeces and compost.

The core experiment was the **quantification of 26 qPCR targets** (TaqMan) in all samples. The targets included **24 antibiotic resistance genes (ARGs)** and **two mobile genetic elements (MGEs)**. These ARGs inactivated aminoglycosides (*aadA*, *nptII*, *nptIII*, *strB*), β -lactams (*bla_{CTX-M-15}*, *bla_{KPG}*, *bla_{NDM-1}*, *bla_{OXA-10}*, *bla_{TEM-1}*, *mecA*), phenicols (*cmxA*), diaminopyrimidines (*dfrA-1*); macrolides (*ermB*, *ermF*), polypeptides (*mcr-1*), biocides (*qacEdelta1*), fluoroquinolones (*qnrS*), nucleosides (*sat-4*),

sulfonamides (*sul1*), tetracyclines (*tet(A)*, *tet(M)*, *tet(O)*, *tet(W)*), and glycopeptides (*vanA*). These ARGs embrace a total of **12 clinically important antibiotic classes** and cover **six different resistance mechanisms**. MGEs-specific genes were *intl1* and *ISPps*. The **16S rRNA gene** was also quantified as a surrogate marker for total soil bacterial abundance and to calculate relative ARG abundances. From each sample, three biological sample replicates were quantified in three technical PCR replicates, each. The combination of absolute and relative quantification and the high number of replicates made the results highly reliable.

The following **analyses** were performed in selected samples, additionally:

- In 81 samples, the diversity and taxonomic composition of the bacterial microflora was analyzed using **Illumina MiSeq 16S amplicon sequencing**. Co-occurrence network analyses established correlations between the distribution of specific organisms and the abundance of individual ARGs, identifying potential bacterial ARG carriers.
- Thirty samples were screened for an expanded spectrum of 95 ARGs using the **Resistomap** SmartChip system, and in 12 of these samples the spectrum was further expanded to 143 targets to provide an in-depth overview of the occurrence of clinically relevant ARGs in the environmental compartments analyzed.
- **Resistance rates of culturable bacteria** to six different antibiotics were determined in 5 soil samples. 213 resistant bacterial isolates were taxonomically identified using *16S rRNA* sequences.
- Sixteen samples were analyzed for 29 different **antibiotics** by **LC-MS/MS**, and 5 additional samples were analyzed for 20 antibiotics.
- The most important **soil parameters** such as pH, texture, humus content, macronutrients, heavy metals and trace elements were determined for 38 soil samples and analyzed for correlations with the qPCR results.
- **Meteorological data** such as temperature, barometric pressure, humidity, rainfall, and wind speed were obtained from the weather station in the HOAL area and from ZAMG weather stations near the monitoring sites for the observation period and analyzed for correlations with the qPCR results.

Overall, the **qPCR results** showed high ARG diversity in the soils. Of 26 targets analyzed, 22 were detected in the HOAL agricultural fields, of which 21 were in turn also found in non-agricultural comparator sites. Roughly summarized, the abundance of detectable targets varied between 10^2 and 10^6 copies per gram of dry soil in the long-term manured HOAL fields with few negative individual samples and between 10^2 and 10^5 copies in the long-term manure-free field F04 again with few negative individual samples. In the comparator soils, the over-all abundance-range was between 10^2 and 10^5 with numerous negative individual samples.

Analysis of swine manure and **comparison of the four HOAL fields** provided evidence that the abundance of 15 targets in agricultural soils is increased by manure fertilization (*ermF*, *ermB*, *dfrA-1*, *sat-4*, *nptIII*, *strB*, *aadA*, *cmxA*, *sul1*, *qacEdelta1*, *tet(A)*, *tet(M)*, *tet(O)*, *tet(W)*, *intl1*). First, these targets had much higher abundance in manure than in soils, with 10^6 to 10^9 copies per gram of dry matter. Second, for thirteen of these targets (all except *aadA* and *tet(O)*) in field F31, a notable ARG concentration peak (maximum value) occurred one day to one week after manure fertilization, which leveled off again to the baseline level (= situation before manure application) by the end of the vegetation period. The increase in concentration was particularly pronounced for *ermF*, which was detectable exclusively in the week after manure fertilization. For *ermF* and *ermB*, this short-term manure effect was also repeated in the second freshly manure-fertilized field F39, but for most other targets the manure-induced increase was not or only very weakly observable, so that static confirmation was not possible. Third, 13 of the aforementioned 15 targets (all except *ermF* and *intl1*) were more abundant in the long-term manure-fertilized fields F31, F32, and F39 than in the long-term manure-free field F04 over the entire observation period. This long-term effect of manure fertilization was statistically significant (ANOVA with Tukey's pairwise post-hoc comparisons, $p < 0.05$). Thus, HOAL agricultural soils were found to be resilient to ARG inputs from manure in the short term, decreasing to baseline-levels within one cropping season (F31) or remaining undetectable in the noise of seasonal fluctuations (F39). At the same time, repeated manure application over years resulted in a permanent increase in concentration of ARGs in cropland soils that was not reversible within a season without manure (F32). In drainage water, the abundance of the investigated targets fluctuated strongly without a clear correlation with manure fertilization.

The same spectrum of ARGs was detected at **the non-agricultural comparator sites** as in the HOAL fields. However, the number of targets detected per individual sample was lower. It varied from 4 to 18 targets per sample at the comparator sites. The lowest values were observed at coniferous forest sites in the Vienna Basin and in the HOAL coniferous forest (NF), the highest on anthropogenically strongly affected grasslands in Vienna. The long-term manure-free field F04 was comparable to grasslands in Vienna with 12 to 18 targets detected. The long-term manure-fertilized fields F31, F39 and F32 were at the upper edge or above the range of variation of the comparator soils with 15 to 19 detected targets. Mainly 10 targets were responsible for this overall picture: *dfrA-1*, *nptIII*, *strB*, *aadA*, *sat-4*, *sul1*, *qacEdelta1*, *tet(A)*, *tet(M)*, *tet(O)*. They were rarely detected at the comparator sites in the Vienna Basin and frequently detected in the Vienna grass plots. Moreover, they were significantly more abundant in fields F31, F39 and F32 than in (almost) all comparator sites (ANOVA with Tukey's pairwise post-hoc comparisons, $p < 0.05$). In field F04, nine of these targets (all except *dfrA-1*) were more abundant than at individual comparator sites, but not more abundant than in the Vienna grass plots. Thus, these 10 targets showed increased abundance in cropland compared to non-cropland in addition to the manure effect (= peak) in the HOAL fields.

For *intl1*, *tet(W)*, *ermB*, and *cmxA*, in addition to the manure effect at the HOAL fields, ubiquitous distribution was found at the comparator sites, contrary to expectations, and for *ermF* frequent occurrence was found in the grasslands and

deciduous forest sites in Vienna. *Mcr-1* was more frequent at the comparator sites than at the HOAL fields.

For the remaining targets, neither a manure effect nor significant differences between cropland and comparator soils were observed. *Bla_{TEM-1}*, *vanA* and *ISPps* were detected ubiquitously and with constant concentration over time. *MecA*, *bla_{OXA-10}* and *nptIII* were detected only selectively in single samples from different sites. *QnrS*, *bla_{CTX-M-15}*, *bla_{KPC}* and *bla_{NDM-1}* were not detected in any soil sample.

16S rRNA gene amplicon sequencing was performed for 68 soil samples, 5 organic fertilizers (1x compost, 1x pig faeces, 3x pig manure) and 8 water samples. Per sample 20 000 - 40 000 high quality filtered sequences were analyzed. Bacterial diversity was generally higher in the soil samples than in water samples and organic fertilizers. The genera *Clostridium sensu stricto 1*, *Terrisporobacter*, *Turicibacter* and *Romboutsia* were detected particularly frequently in pig manure and in the manured fields, with a strong increase after manure application. These data suggest that these bacteria were introduced into the soil from the manure. *Clostridium sensu stricto 1* was also detected with low read counts (<30) in the drainage and in 75% of the stream water samples. In a network analysis, the correlation of antibiotic resistance gene concentrations with the frequency of bacterial genera was investigated. In particular, the bacterium *Terrisporobacter* was identified as a potential resistance gene carrier, since the antibiotic resistance genes *dfrA-1*, *nptIII*, *sat-4* and the antiseptic resistance gene *qacEdelta1* correlated positively with this genus according to Spearman.

In addition, bacterial species or genera that could be clinically relevant were identified in the samples analyzed. These included *Aeromonas*, *Bacillus*, *Flavobacterium* and *Pseudomonas*. These genera have been documented as both environmental bacteria as well as pathogens of nosocomial infections.

The investigation of 95 targets in faeces, manure, 8 HOAL field samples and 20 reference soils with the **Resistomap SmartChip** system impressively showed the high ARG diversity in soils. In the comparator soils, the number of detected targets per sample varied between 37 and 62. HOAL fields F04 and F32 were within this range with 55 to 60 detected targets, fields F31 and F39 with 60 to 69 targets were above. A striking feature of the Resistomap result was a constant ranking from abundant to rare targets across all soil samples. The most abundant targets in the soils were *intl-1*, *mexF*, *ermE* and *vanA*. While individual targets were missing in the soil samples depending on location and time, the whole spectrum was detected in a single sample in pig faeces and manure and there was a different abundance ranking compared to soil. The manure was dominated by tetracycline resistance genes, which were rare in the soil. In manure/faeces and arable soils, 15 common targets were identified that were not found in the comparator soils (*ermF*, *bla_{TEM-1}*, *tetQ*, *tetM_3*, *tetA(P)*, *tetO_1*, *tetM_2*, *tetO_2*, *tetX*, *qacEdelta1_3*, *qacEdelta1_1*, *fosX*, *aadE*, *aphA3_1*, *tnpA_1*). In 12 comparator soils from the Donau-Auen National Park and the Ötscher region, 48 additional targets were investigated. This led to the detection of another 13 to 25 targets per sample and once again highlighted the high ARG diversity in near-natural soils.

Cultivable bacteria from one sample each from the long-term manure-free field F04, the manured field F31, 2 sites in the Donau-Auen National Park and one manure sample were tested for resistance to vancomycin, kanamycin, sulfadiazine, ampicillin, erythromycin and tetracycline. Cultivable bacteria resistant to each of these antibiotics were detected in all samples. Resistance rates were determined as the proportion of resistant bacteria to the total number of culturable bacteria. For vancomycin and kanamycin, resistance rates were highest in the Donau-Auen soils (DA01 and DA10) and in the non-manure-fertilized field (F04). The sulfadiazine resistance rate was elevated in one of the Donau-Auen samples (DA10) and low in all other samples. For ampicillin, the resistance rate was similar in all soil samples and very low in the manure. The erythromycin resistance rate was low in all samples. The tetracycline resistance rate was also low in all samples, with the highest value in manure-fertilized field F31. In the manure, the total number of culturable bacteria was 10-fold and 100-fold higher than in the soil samples.

To identify potential ARG carriers, vancomycin-, kanamycin-, sulfadiazine-, ampicillin-, erythromycin- and tetracycline-**resistant bacteria were isolated** from each of the 5 samples. A total of 213 isolates were taxonomically classified by *16S rRNA* gene sequences. The most common genera among the resistant soil isolates were *Pseudomonas*, *Pedobacter*, *Variovorax* and *Stenotrophomonas*, among the pig manure isolates they were *Brevibacterium*, *Enterococcus* and *Bavariicoccus*.

To determine the selection pressure, the **concentration of 29 different antibiotics** was determined in 14 representatively selected soil samples, one faeces and one manure sample. One drainage water sample and four stream water samples were analyzed for 20 antibiotics. Only in manure a fluoroquinolone (marbofloxacin: 20.8 µg/kg) and a tetracycline derivative (doxycycline: 102.0 µg/kg) were detected. In a HOAL stream water sample, a sulfonamide (sulfadimidine: < 0.0010 µg/L) could be qualitatively detected but not quantified. The detected amounts of marbofloxacin and doxycycline exceed the minimum selective concentrations (MSC) reported for some bacterial species/antibiotic combinations and could therefore favor the growth of resistant bacterial strains in the manure.

In the **correlation analysis**, a negative correlation was observed between target abundance and rainfall on the day of sampling for nine targets. Individual targets also correlated with other meteorological factors or certain soil parameters. For instance, *tet(O)* and *tet(M)* correlated positively with the detected amounts of copper in soil, whereas *tet(W)* negatively correlated with soil- and air-temperature.

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